

Assessment of Early Counseling Technique on Future Education among Public Primary School Pupils in North-Central, Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper examined assessment of Early Counselling Technique on Future Education among Public Primary School Pupils in, North-Central Nigeria. It raised two research questions, two and corresponding null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance to guide the study. Survey Research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study consists of entire public primary school's pupils during the 2022/2023 academic session in North-Central Nigeria. The sample of the study comprised of 30 pupils who were selected using purposive sampling technique, 5 schools from each State in north central. Questionnaire titled Early Counselling for Future Education (ECFE) was used to collect information from the respondents. The instrument was weighted on four (4) point scale of SD, A, DA SDA. The instrument was validated by 3 experts in the fields of Psychology, and measurement and evaluation from Federal College of Education, Zaria. Simple percentage was used to answer the research questions and t-test was used to analyze the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The results revealed that there is statistically significant relationship between early counselling and future Education in North-Central, Nigeria. It is also revealed that there is statistically significant relationship between follow up counselling service and future education. It was concluded that early counselling has significant impact on future education and follow-up service has positive influence on future education in North-Central, Nigeria. It was recommended that early counselling for future Education should be encouraged. And also, follow-up service in counselling should be supported by government to revive future Education in north-central, Nigeria.

Keywords: Early Counselling Techniques, Future Education and Public-School Pupils.

Introduction

The elementary school level of education is the most important in all education levels. It is for this reason that it is labeled primary school. The primary school, is but part of the early education processes that prepares a child for the secondary school, among other numerous benefits. It is important to note here that both the primary school teachers and parents of the pupils join hands to mold the mind of the child to a meaningful status (Egbo, 2015).

The need to institute counselling programmes in primary school cannot be over emphasized. Human mind at this level is usually in a "tabular rasa" form. This implies that the mind of the child, at this level is virgin and open, needs to be filled up. By virtues of good counselling and subsequent training, the pupil begins to develop positively. This is what task this paper explores using guidance and counselling as a prolific tool for effective human living and adjustment. Thus, guidance and counseling are remedial, preventive and developmental. It takes care of the needs of the pupils to demonstrate adjustment and maturity in relationships and cushion possible discovery of their talents, abilities, potentialities, strengths and weakness at the earliest stages for their own betterment. The need for pupils to live functional and meaningful lives makes it imperative that early guidance and counseling programmes should be established at the primary school level. The aim is to enhance early and positive adjustment procedures for meaningful living.

Guidance is a programme of service meant to enhance the ability of clients to cope with circumstances and be of need to themselves and the society. Guidance enables clients to make choices which are intended to bring self-direction and adjustment. It is designed to help clients adjust meaningfully to the environment, develop the ability to set realistic goals and improve on total educational programmes Egbo, (2015). Thus, Zera and Riccio in Omebe (2016) defined guidance as a process, developmental in nature, by which an individual is assisted to understand, accept and utilize own abilities, aptitudes, interests and attitudinal patterns in relation to the aspirations. As well, Isakson and Minsk in Omebe (2016) see guidance as a programme of service to individuals based on the needs of each individual; an understanding of his immediate environment and the influences of the factors on the learner and unique features of the school. This is why counselling assists each pupil to

understand himself, accept himself and live effectively in his society in addition to having learning experiences about his world of work (Alao, 2021). Pupils' right from school start preparation for the world of work and should be properly guided in educational, personal –social and vocational spheres of life in order to make right choices.

Ipaye (2014) upholds that guidance in everyday language has always carried the connotation of help given to an individual or group of individuals in areas like personal, social, educational and vocational which are designed to ensure meaningful adjustment in their existence. Good guidance programmes organized for learners at the primary school level are therefore intended to actualize positivity in whole life adjustment meant to cushion the growing child into meaningful living and adaptations. Counselling, on the other hand is the soul of the guidance programme, and the wheel upon which guidance rotates. It is a process in which a specialist counsellor undertakes to assist another person in a person to person or face to face encounter. The assistance may take many forms which includes educational, vocational, social, recreational, emotional and or moral, and this could be organized in groups or individually. Thus, Roux in Anagbogu (2022) defines counselling as a dynamic and purposeful relationship between two people in which procedures vary with the nature of the students' needs, but in which there is always mutual participation by the counsellor and the client with the focus of self-actualization and self-determination by the client.

Counselling is a relationship characterized by mutual respect, effective communication, genuine and complete acceptances of the client by the counsellor and concentration on the needs, problems and feelings of the clients. It is also relationship that facilitates growth and changes in the client to become more freely and fully functional. It is a major service that is incorporated in guidance which is but an interactive process between a counsellor and the client, meant to enhance proper self-understanding for the client to have better behavioural changes. Thus, Anagbogu (2022) affirms that individuals strive to achieve optimal development of personal resources and that counselling aid the children in developing the most effective ways of identifying and achieving desired and desirable goals for better adjustment and living. That means that counselling prevents frustrations, anxieties and stress. Follow-up services enable the guidance counsellor to see through the services he/she must have offered the counsellee. It is an avenue through which the counsellor determines the effectiveness of planning and placement activities. Sokan and Osarenren (2015).

The North Central is one of the six (6) geo-political zones of Nigeria. Also known as middle belt. It comprises of 6 states. Namely, Benue, Kogi, Kwara, Nasarawa, Niger, Plateau and Federal Capital Territory (FCT). The North Central stretching across the whole range of the country, from the border with Cameroon to that with Benin. In terms of the terrain, the zone is predominantly known to be farmers and are blessed with fertile land for farming. The region has a population of about 20 Million people, which is about 11th population of the entire population of the country. The counselling service allows the counsellor to see and verify whether the guided or counseled individual or group is coping after guidance or counselling.

The entire functions of the guidance counsellor in the school setting are to assist each student to understand himself and live effectively in the society. The need for guidance services in the school system is therefore based on the assumption that the individual who understands himself and his environment will be more productive and effective in his entire endeavour. The objectives which the functions performed by the guidance counsellor in the school system according to Ijale & Umaru (2021) includes:

1. To help pupils develop the skills of self-study, self-analysis and self-understanding.
2. Guidance services should help pupils develop awareness of opportunities in the personal, social, educational, vocational areas by providing them with appropriate, useful and useable information.
3. Also, guidance services in the school should help pupils acquire the skills of collecting and using appropriate information.
4. To assist all pupils in making appropriate and satisfactory personal, social, educational, vocational and leisure choices.
5. Counselling service should help pupils develop positive attitude to self, to others, mental health, to appropriate national issues, to work and learning.
6. To help pupils acquire as early as possible in their lives a positive image of themselves through self-understanding and self-direction.
7. Counselling services should help pupils who are under achieving to use their potentials to the maximum.
8. Also, counselling services in the school should help pupils relate behaviour meaningfully to cognitive achievement and the chances of success in life.
9. To help build up or sharpen the staff's perception of reality, development of a sense of autonomy and to whip up the motivation for creativity and productivity.

10. Guidance services in the schools should assist pupils in the process of developing and acquiring skills in problem solving and decision making.
11. To work with significant others in the life of pupils by helping them to understand the needs and problems of the pupils with the purpose of creating, arousing and sustaining their interest in and their understanding of the staff' needs, problems and goals so that the pupils can be optimally helped to attain their goals, handle these problems and those needs.
12. To help route the nation's human resources into appropriate, useful and beneficial channels thus preventing unnecessary economic wastage.
13. Guidance services should help identify and nurture human potentialities in various fields or endeavours thus ensuring adequate manpower development in various sectors of the economy.
14. To help build up in individuals' positive attitude to fellow Nigerians and a sense of total commitment to the unity of Nigeria.

Elementary School Counselling: The Federal Republic of Nigeria (2004) views the objectives of primary school education to include:

1. The inculcation of permanent literacy, and the ability to communicate effectively
2. The laying of a sound basis for scientific and reflective thinking
3. Citizenship education as a basis for effective participation as contribution to the life of the society.
4. Development in the child, the ability to adapt to his changing environment
5. Providing the child with opportunities for developing manipulative skills that will enable him function effectively the society within the limits of his capacity and
6. Providing basic tools for further educational advancement including preparation trades and crafts of the society.

Transplanting of trees are usually done only when such tree species are seedlings. Tall palm trees can hardly be transplanted. Primary school pupils are tender in age, ranging between six to thirteen years. This makes counselling at this level very paramount and different from counselling at other levels of education. It is at this elementary stage that we can really identify and begin to nurture the potentials of the primary school children to maturity. Based on this, relegating and deferring elementary school counselling are but intentional deferment to the developmental growth of the children which is senseless and cannot be sustained. The best time to frame good behavioural patterns and characteristics in people is at the elementary school stage. At this stage the pupils are still innocent and open to accommodate facts which at maturity (secondary and tertiary), they easily shed off some and retain some.

The primary school children are at the stage of formation of identity and self-concept. They are open to a myriad of options and that is why guidance and counselling services are supposed to be prevalent at this stage because it is better to train pupils than to mend men. The Universal Basic Education in Nigeria in 1976 and the subsequent National Policy on Education are but strategies designed to sustain zeal for education, skill and development in Nigerian school children. They are both fashioned out for functional, universal and qualitative education among Nigerian youths. This is why guidance and counselling services should be provided at the elementary school stage to nurture the development and growth of the school pupils. Thus, Ipaye (2014) writes prophetically that no matter how good and well-structured the new educational policy in Nigeria may be, if guidance and counselling services are not given priority, and made an integral part of the system, it cannot succeed. This is all because the school counsellors in primary schools work with teachers, parents, head teachers and the pupils to induce effectiveness, adjustment and wellbeing of the pupils.

Essence of Primary School Guidance and Counseling

1. Construct alternative behaviour
2. Seek relevant information about alternatives
3. Weigh values and possible outcomes and
4. Formulates tentative plans of action

The counsellor therefore is expected to emphasis therapeutic principles in teaching and counseling the pupils for efficient learning processes. The primary school children therefore need counselling for the following reasons:

1. Need to tap and harness the individual pupils' ability, interest, personality, talents and aptitude starts at this level for their developmental growth.
2. Need to provide special help for numerous primary school children to avert possible crimes and health hazards
3. Need to stem the tide of maladaptive behaviours in the school system and the general public
4. Need to identify and nurture the gifted and talented children
5. Need for behavioural changes as many homes now breed social problems

6. Need for outreach counselling especially as many homes are impoverished
7. Need to provide the child with a sound foundation for future, academic, psychological and personal growth

The need for counselling at the primary school system, according to Durojaiye in Egbo (2016) emanate from the fact that the Nigerian family had experienced significant changes that had resulted in breakdown of family cohesiveness and increased rate of divorce. This has significantly increased the one parent home trend and subsequent increment in deviant behaviours among children because:

1. Divorce and its accompanying strains continue to increase
2. Children are being reared differently and more frequently by outsiders (maids or day care givers)
3. Mothers are plagued by the guilt of leaving their children to go to work
4. Parents generally do not have time to monitor their primary school children.

Consequently, primary school teachers and counsellors need to understand the unique characteristics and nature of each pupil as well as be able to make relative referrals at any point in time. Good classroom and social and social climate should be created for inclusive development of the pupils for maximum sustenance of solutions to academic, vocational and personal social problems of the Nigerian primary school pupils

Counselling is oriented towards facilitating effective learning skills, acceptable habits and appropriate behaviour in individual. It is a process through which individuals can understand themselves fully. Within the school system it should be a learning process in which individuals learn about themselves, their interpersonal relationship and behaviours that advance their personal development. However, pupils in primary schools currently are not properly guided or counseled as it ought to be and as such the future education is jeopardized (Bledsoe, 2018). Many pupils learn negatively and peer influence is the order of the day Udoh and George (2014). Reorientation and early counselling can go along to impact pupils positively and assurance for future education in north central, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

1. To examine the impact of early counselling on future education among Public Primary School Pupils in North central.
2. To examine the influence of follow-up service on future education among Public Primary School Pupils in North central.

Research Questions.

1. What is the impact of early counselling on future education among Public Primary School Pupils in north central, Nigeria?
2. What is the influence of follow-up counselling service on future education among Public Primary School Pupils in north central Nigeria?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant impact between early counselling and future education among Public Primary School Pupils in north central, Nigeria
2. There is no significant influence between follow- up service and future education among Public Primary School Pupils in North Central, Nigeria

Methodology

The Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. This design is considered appropriate because it enables the researchers to generate data through the standardized collection procedures based on highly structured research instrument(s) and well-defined study concepts and related variables.

The population of this study was made up of 30 pupils in north central, Nigeria. Five (5) schools were selected from each state, and Ten (10) pupils were purposively selected.

A well-constructed and researcher developed Questionnaire titled Early Counselling for Future Education (ECFE) was used to collect information from the respondents. The instrument was weighted on four (4) point scale of SD, A, DA SA. The instrument was validated by 3 experts in the field of Psychology and measurement and evaluation from FCE, Zaria. Simple percentage and t-test was used to analyze the hypotheses.

The questionnaire was divided into three sections (A, B and C). Section A was for collection of information on personal data of the respondents while Section B consisted of early counselling questionnaire that elicited responses from the respondents on the impact on counselling services and future education section C contains information on the influence of

follow-up services on future education among primary school pupils in north central Nigeria. The section B and C had response options scored thus: Strongly Agree (SA) =4, Agree (A) = 3 Disagree (D) =2 and Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1. Simple percentage and t-test was used to analyze the hypotheses.

Presentation of Results

Paired Samples Statistics

Research Question one

What is the impact of early counselling on future education among Public Primary School Pupils in north?

Table 1: The impact of early counselling on future education among Public Primary School Pupils in north central, Nigeria.

	Respondents			
	A	SA	D	SD
1. Early counselling could help in future education	50 47.6%	40 38.1%	10 9.5%	5 4.8%
2. Functional counselling at pre-primary to higher education is grantee for better education	60 57.1%	30 28.6%	8 7.6%	7 6.7%
3. Early counselling is very impact in future education	55 52.4%	40 38.1%	10 9.5%	0 0.0%
4. Effective counselling direct pupils on future education	45 42.9%	40 38.1%	15 14.3%	5 4.8%
5. Early counselling help pupils to understand the aim of education	70 66.7%	20 19.0%	5 4.8%	10 9.5%
6. Counselling pupils enhanced understanding of oneself the environment	40 38.1%	55 52.4%	7 6.7%	3 2.9%
7. Early counselling help pupils to be focus and achieve their educational goals.	50 47.6%	45 42.9%	5 4.8%	5 4.8%

Table 1 above shows that early counselling could be of help in future education, 50 respondents representing 47% strongly agree with the statement, 40 respondents representing 38.1% agree, 10 respondents representing 9.5% strongly disagree with the statement while 5 respondents representing 4.8% disagree with the statement. It means that early counselling public primary school could be of help in future education. Functional counselling at pre-primary to higher education is grantee for better education, early counselling is has a significant impact in future education, effective counseling direct pupils on future education, early counselling help pupils to understand the aim of education, counselling pupils enhanced understanding of oneself in the environment and early counselling help pupils to be focus and achieve their education goals, 90 respondents representing 90% strongly agree, agree with the all the statement above while 10 respondents representing 10% strongly disagree, disagree respectively, this connote that the above statement has a positive significant on pupils in public primary school in Zaria Metropolis.

Research Question Two

What is the influence of follow-up counselling service on future education among Public Primary School Pupils in north central Nigeria?

Table 2: The influence of follow-up counselling service on future education among Public Primary School Pupils in north central Nigeria

	Respondents			
	A	SA	D	SD
1. Follow up service in counselling helps to redirect.	52.4%	38.1%	9.5%	0.0%
2. Follow up enhances consistency in pupils education pursuit.	55 66.7%	40 19.0%	10 4.8%	0 9.5%
3. Following by both counsellors and government agency only way for better education	70 38.1%	20 52.4%	5 6.7%	10 2.9%
	40	55	7	3

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4. Further education can be revitalized through follow up service by counsellors.	57.1%	19.0%	19.0%	4.8%
5. Consistent and proper counselling service to schools and ministry of education is a system to further education	47.6%	42.9%	9.5%	0.0%
6. Future education is guaranteed with effective service and proper supervision	52.4%	42.9%	4.8%	0.0%
	60	20	20	5
	50	45	10	0
	55	45	5	0

Table 2 above shows that follow-up service in counselling helps to redirect, 52.4% of the respondents agree, 38.1 strongly agree, 9.5% disagree with the statement while 0.0% strongly disagree. There is no doubt that follow up service in counselling helps to redirect pupils among public primary schools. Furthermore, follow-up enhances consistency in pupils education pursuit, following by both counsellors and government agency only way for better education, further education can be revitalized through follow-up service by counsellors, consistent and proper counselling service to schools and ministry of education is a system to further education and future education is guaranteed with effective service and proper supervision. All the respondents agree, strongly agree with the statement above.

Hypotheses One

There is no significant impact between early counselling and future education among Public Primary School Pupils in north central, Nigeria

	Mean	N	Std. Dev	Std. error mean	d.f	Correlation	T.cal	P-val
Counselling service	2.11	105	.923	.090	104	.246	.252	.028
Future education	2.09	105	.972	.095				

Table 3. Since the P-value (0.028) is less than 0.05, and accept the null hypothesis.

The result revealed that there is a statistically significant impact of Counselling Services Future on education (t.cal= .252, df= 105, p<0.05). This means that there is positive impact of Counselling Services on Future Education. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Hypotheses Two: 2

There is no significant influence between follow- up service and future education among Public Primary School Pupils in North Central, Nigeria

	Mean	N	Std. Dev	Std. error mean	Correlation	T.cal	Sig
Follow-up service	1.97	105	.885	.086		0.531	2.235
Future education	2.09	105	.972	.095			.021

Table 4. Since the P-value (0.021) is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis was accepted and the result revealed that there is a statistically significant influence of follow- up Counselling Services on Future education (t.cal= 2.235, df= 104, p<0.05). This means that there is positive influence of Following Service on Future Education. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Discussion of Findings

The result revealed that there is a statistically significant impact of Counselling Services Future on education (t.cal= .252, df= 105, p<0.05). This means that there is positive impact of Counselling techniques on Future Education. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. The result is in agreement with Egbo (2015) which stated that counselling is designed to help clients adjust meaningfully to the environment, develop the ability to set realistic goals and improve on total educational programmes.. The result revealed that there is a statistically significant influence of follow- up Counselling Services on Future education (t.cal= 2.235, df= 104, p<0.05). This means that there is positive influence of Following Service on Future Education. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This result is in line with Ipaye (2014) who writes prophetically that no matter how

good and well-structured the new educational policy in Nigeria may be, if guidance and counselling services are not given priority, and made an integral part of the system, it cannot succeed. This is all because the school counsellors in primary schools work with teachers, parents, head teachers and the pupils to induce effectiveness, adjustment and wellbeing of the pupils.

Conclusion

Based on the finding, the study concludes:

1. That there is significant impact of early counselling and future education.
2. There is significant influence of follow-service on future education.

Recommendation

It is therefore recommended that

1. Early counselling will enhance and redeem future Education.
2. It is also recommended that follow-up service in counselling and government support will further revive future Education in north central.
3. Finally, it was recommended that early counselling for future Education should be encouraged.

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